

A Brief Study of Tribal Literature

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Abstract

"Tribal literature" attempts to express the cultural, social, and historical aspects of tribes. The main objective of this literature is to share the unique identity of the tribes, their lifestyle, and their cultural heritage. This literature supports their identity through language, songs, stories, and poems.

Keywords

Tribal Literature, Tribe, Literature.

Introduction

The literature of tribes is an integral part of expressing their unique cultural heritage. This literature is dedicated to the self-identity of those tribes, their historical and cultural heritage, and their socio-economic lives.

1. Diversity and variation: The literature on tribes keeps diversity and variation vital. It has a variety of languages, styles, and art and music forms that reveal its unique cultural identity.

2. Experiences of life: The literature of the tribes embodies the experiences of life. It contains diverse descriptions of his physical, spiritual, and social backgrounds, reflecting his prosperity and struggle.

3. Historical journey: This literature contains details of the historical trip of the tribes. It promotes the struggles and successes of their great warriors, kings, and social leaders.

4. Local style and language: The literature of tribes follows local type and language. It contains their unique languages, folklore, and grammar, which highlight their roles, thoughts, and feelings.

5. Social message: The literature of tribes keeps the social messages meaningful. This discusses the topics of change in their society, the direction of prosperity, and self-reliance.

6. Conservation and promotion: The literature of the tribes encourages a feeling of their natural richness and conservation. It covers wildlife issues, the importance of natural resources, and environmental protection.

The literature of the tribes is a medium that helps them address their self-enrichment, cultural identity, and society. This helps carry forward their unique story, role, and legacy and brings a remarkable literary gift to life.

1) Objective of the Tribal Literature

The literature of tribes is part of a unique cultural richness in which their society, historical heritage, and lifestyle are studied literarily. Here is a description of the main objectives of the literature on the tribes.

1. Preservation of cultural heritage: The literature of the tribes plays an essential role in preserving their unique cultural heritage. It examines their ancestors' lifestyles, art, music, dance, and other cultural aspects and conveys them through literature.

2. Structure of historical knowledge: The literature of the tribes works to structure their historical knowledge. It discusses the development of their society, historical events, and the lives of prominent personalities, which connects future generations to their history.

3. Literary creation and prosperity: The literature of the tribes works to promote their literary output. It presents paths to diversity and wealth through their literary art, poems, stories, and songs.

4. Awareness of social justice and prosperity: tribal literature raises awareness of social justice, harmony, and prosperity. It contains messages through stories, poems, and songs to guide them towards change in their society.

5. Support for social and economic prosperity: The literature of the tribes supports social and economic prosperity. It focuses on their society's development, education, health, and economic prosperity.

The literature of the Samiti tribes is a tool that guides them towards their prosperity, cultural preservation, and justice and harmony in society. Its Objective is to help them become self-reliant and prosperous.

2) Folklore is an ocean of unique stories about people's lives.

An essential part of Indian literature is folklore, which we can call an ocean of unique stories of people's lives. This literature is in the language of the tribal, rural, and general public and works to touch on their cultural currents, habits, and experiences.

i. Nature of folklore: folklore is literature that tries to touch every aspect of people's lives. It can manifest in various forms, such as songs, stories, tales, chants, dances, plays, etc. Its main objective is to address people and try to make them understand their uniqueness. Folk literature has been alive since the beginning. Folk songs, stories, and dances sung in villages still enrich our cultural heritage.

ii. Importance of Folklore—Richness and Cultural Growth Folklore has preserved our rich and diverse cultural heritage. We understand our ancestors' lifestyle, customs, and cultural richness through this. **Social Reform:** Folklore is a unique instrument for social Reform. Its tales and songs highlight social problems and inspire people towards a prosperous society. **Language and Literature** Folklore keeps the language alive and spreads it among the people. It helps in maintaining the beauty and literary form of the language. **Representation of public life:** Folklore represents the reality of public life and touches on the commoner's lifestyle, celebrations, and joys. Folklore provides us with a unique medium to understand our cultural heritage. It shares the roles hidden in the depths of human life and reminds us of the importance of struggle, love, and harmony with each other. Its exchange remains constant in our rich literary heritage.

3) Tribal literature and folklore are different forms of Indian literature, and their differences exist.

i. More stability of situation: tribal literature often expresses the language, culture, and traditions of people of particular tribes or communities. In this, the tribes' thoughts, feelings, and histories are introduced.

Folklore is associated with social richness and reflects the standard life views, problems, and conventions of the people of different communities. It covers a large area and is shaped by the local cultural perspective in other regions.

ii. Theme and Basis: Tribal Literature It focuses on the social, cultural, and historical subjects of the tribes. It strives to maintain its own cultural relevance and historical richness.

Folklore includes individuals, society, and social problems. It is based on social prosperity, especially the life issues of ordinary people, love, celebration of life, and their experiences.

iii. Language and Style: Tribal literature is often written in the local language of the tribes and reflects their specific culture.

Folklore includes a variety of tales, poems, and songs written in the language and style of different languages and regions.

iv. Types and Objectives: Tribal Literature Its Main Objective is to save and promote the cultural and historical heritage of the tribes.

The primary purpose of folklore is to increase social awareness, teach people through stories, and promote cultural mutual understanding among people. These differences lie in the perspective of form, purpose, and subject, but both contribute to the richness of Indian literature in their ways.

4) Nuances of tribal literature

i. Starting points: The literature of the tribes forms an integral part of Indian literature, which they retain through their unique role and heritage. This literature has a quality that supports their life, culture, and history. In this part of literature, tribal literature symbolizes a unique perspective and creativity.

ii. Language and role: The literature of the tribes is unique in their language, which reveals their particular cultural and social identity. It reflects their emotional ties to the land, environment, and social relations. The speech promotes the abstract sensibility of this literature and embodies its role and ideas in its unique language.

iii. Subject matter and literary framework: The literature of the tribes includes essential aspects of their lives, which is representative of their interestingness and emotionality. Various tales, sagas, and folktales represent their rich cultural heritage. In the literary framework, this literature has a special place that reflects their artistic talent.

The nuances of tribal literature teach us that literature is not just a collection of words. Still, it is a significant source of prosperity that supports society and inspires it towards the highest standards.

Objective of study

1. Study on the literature of tribes.
2. Present status of tribal literature.

Review of Literature

The literature of the tribes is part of a profound and ancient cultural heritage whose history goes back thousands of years. This literature contributes significantly to realizing the role, culture, and lifestyle of those tribes.

1. The literature of the tribes started in ancient times and has been helping preserve their historical and cultural heritage. During this period, oral traditions and sagas were the central parts of literature that chronicled historical events, wars, and the goodwill of the tribes.

2. Mediaeval period Even during the medieval period, the literature of the tribes continued to develop, and work was done to save their cultural traditions. During this time, written literature flourished in abundance, including religious texts, poems, and stories from the tribes.

3. In recent years, the literature of the tribes has also continuously developed; in this, technological advancement, education, and social changes are studied. Writers and artists support the ideas of tribes through their literary products in new and modern forms.

4. Main Themes and Influences The main themes of tribal literature focus on diversity, cultural tradition, and the life experiences of their society. It contains descriptions of wildlife, cultural practices, and other natural wonders that reveal their distinct cultural identity.

The literature of the tribes is a form of symbolism of their uniqueness and pride, which preserves their historical, cultural, and social development and helps them move toward prosperity.

Many vital books on tribal literature have been written that examine the literature of Indian tribes from a sociological perspective and consider their attitudes toward their society, culture, and language. Critically studies and highlights his thoughtfulness along with an analysis of the feminist tradition in tribal literature, a discussion on the diversity and characteristics of literature, an evaluation of makeup language, an Analysis of the development of Indian tribal literature and its monetary framework, a discussion on its integrity and features, and how it conveys change in the form of a social message. The influence of language in tribal literature has been analyzed, and their cultural richness

has been highlighted through language. In which social and political symbols are discussed, and social conflicts can be understood. How can tribal literature be understood as a form of colonization of Indian literature? The role and nature of tribal literature have been discussed so that readers can understand the essential aspects of tribal literature by studying it. Indian tribal literature, art, and culture have given perspective to tribal communities. The historical, cultural, and literary aspects of Indian tribal literature are analyzed. He has talked about the social and academic messages of tribal literature and raised the issue of problems arising from it. The importance of tribal literature has been considered by connecting it with cultural society. The nature of tribal literature and its issues have been discussed. An attempt has been made to explain various aspects of tribal literature in social, cultural, and political contexts. The development, structure, and problems of tribal literature have been discussed in detail.

An attempt has been made to touch upon various dimensions of the literature in detail, and suggestions have been made to support it. An effort has been made to highlight the folk literature of different communities and tribes specifically. Tribal literature has been analysed explicitly in literary, cultural, and social contexts. In this book, essential directions of tribal literature and strategic aspects of modernity have been revealed. The social problems of the tribes have been discussed, and solutions have been presented. Considers the thinking and means of prosperity of tribal communities. A unique study of the literature of Indian tribes has been made, and their literary traditions have been presented. These books can help you study various aspects of tribal literature, academic viewpoints, and problems.

Methodology

This study has been done based on secondary data and observation.

Analysis

Tribes are essential in Indian society, a country of confluence of different castes, religions, and cultural diversities. However, even in this prosperous communal structure, certain conditions do not support the tribes in society, and they have to face anti-tribal atrocities. Anti-tribal literature is an essential means of highlighting this situation of inequality and injustice through social Reform.

Impact of anti-tribal literature Anti-tribal literature highlights the injustice and discrimination against tribes by the people of the highest class in society. This literature creates social awareness and makes the tribes aware of their rights and current situation. Through this, people understand that for a prosperous society, they should be given equal status with the tribes. By propagating this protest in the form of literature, there is a change in society's viewpoint. Poems, stories, and novels written by writers and poets make the community aware and inspire them to advance in society. In the direction of Reform in society, anti-tribal literature works towards bringing about change. Through this, things about social Reform and equality are shared, which makes people aware of the community and inspires them to increase empathy. Through this, a feeling of harmony and equality is created in society, which leads to steps towards a prosperous society. **Conclusion** Anti-tribal literature is a medium that encourages a sense of equality, justice, and harmony in the community. It spreads awareness and works towards providing support and respect to the tribes in the social space. Only through this can society be improved, and work can be done to provide equal rights to people of all classes.

Study of some possibilities and shortcomings in the literature of tribes

Potential

Cultural Enrichment The literature of the tribes tells about their unique cultural heritage, and it can be enriched in the right way. This can bring forward their particular cultural elements, providing a new perspective. The literature of the tribals can better describe the local life, environment, and lifestyle. This helps in taking steps towards the highest level of prosperity. **Proper Utilisation of Material Resources** The literature of the tribes can utilise their material resources properly to lead to their cultural and economic prosperity. **Literary Origins** The literature of the tribes can strengthen their literary origins and turn them towards prosperity and development.

Shortcomings

Lack of education among the tribes can be a main shortcoming, making their literature less effective. This may lead to a reduction in writing and literary expression. Lack of structure and academic development There may be a lack of design and literary development in some tribes, leading to a lack of their literary scheme. **Economic Problems** Some tribes struggle with financial problems, which can dull their literature. It is essential to provide them with support for economic progress. **Lack of awareness of issues:** Sometimes, there is a lack of understanding of social and political issues in the literature of tribes, which may affect their literary plans. Due to the lack of modern technology in some places, there may be difficulty in making tribal literature available to the public. There are possibilities and shortcomings in the literature of indigenous tribes,

but by taking steps in the right direction, these can be changed in the order of prosperity. Literary prosperity requires education, organization, and the proper support from society.

The lack of tribal literature on social media could be due to several reasons

Language and Technology Gap

Most tribal literature is written in our official languages, which are prominently different on social media. As a result, it is not getting good exposure on social media. There may be variations due to technical differences in language and greetings.

Lack of Approach and Support

There may be a lack of direction and support to disseminate literature on specific tribes or communities on social media. Communities face various technical and social challenges.

Due to the dissemination of these on social media to corruption and terrorism, some literature may not be safe to broadcast on social media because its use may lead to crime, terrorism, or increase xenophobic sentiments in society. As a result, social media platforms can control this type of content.

Lack of Diverse Forms of Literature

It can be challenging to disseminate various forms of literature on social media, such as songs, dances, and stories of festivals, which are an essential part of tribal literature.

Lack of high-quality content in communities: Some communities may need more technical knowledge to create high-quality content to disseminate literature on social media. All these reasons can hinder the dissemination of literature from communities on social media.

Some Suggestions to Improve Tribal Literature

1. Rich collection and preservation, first of all, the literature of the tribes should be richly collected and preserved. Various literary organizations can be supported to maintain and share their stories, songs, and art.
2. Embracing technological prosperity It is also essential to use technology correctly. The tribes will be helped to share their literature on various platforms using modern technologies.
3. Dissemination of Tribal Literature Tribal literature can be disseminated through various social media platforms, blogs, and internet sites. This will promote their literary stream and reach new generations.
4. Educational support can become an essential part of education to improve literature. Create and support a curriculum to include tribal literature in local schools and colleges.
5. Literary conferences and festivals It are also a good idea to organize them. This brings the literary community together, and new ideas are exchanged.
6. Establishment of literary awards, the establishment of literary awards can also be a good step. With this, litterateurs can be encouraged and get recognition for their contribution.
7. Supporting Diversity Supporting diversity in literature is also important. Writers from different affluence and geographical perspectives of tribes should be supported so that there can be a basis for stories written from different perspectives.
8. Demonstrations at public places One way to make tribal literature accessible to the general public is to organize demonstrations and book fairs at public places. People can come here and become familiar with tribal literature.
9. Programmes in schools and colleges, organize programs to increase awareness of tribal literature in schools and colleges. Call authors, interact with them, and share their works with students.

10. Community Radio and Television Tribal literature can be disseminated through community radio and local television. This can be an excellent way to reach the locals directly.

11. Tribal Literature Festival, organize a Tribal Literature Festival where writers, poets, and artists from different tribes can showcase their works. Through this festival, people can connect with tribal literature.

12. Support of folk art and culture, Increase support for folk art and culture. Promote tribal literature by linking it with it. Tribal literature also became a part of folk art conferences.

13. Use of social media, tribal literature can also be made available to the general public by using social media. Promote events on platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram and reach online audiences.

14. Translation into languages Tribal literature can also be made available by translating it into different languages. This allows people to experience tribal literature in other languages.

15. Mobile applications and podcasts Tribal literature can also be made available to the general public by using mobile applications and podcasts. Create audio and video content and reach people.

16. Government Schemes, Take advantage of schemes run by the government, such as programmes organized by the Ministry of Tourism and Culture. This can support tribal literature.

17. Community libraries Tribal literature can also be kept in community libraries. Here, people can easily read it and understand its importance.

18. Following these steps and using some new methods makes it possible to make tribal literature accessible to the general public. Understanding democracy and diversity is also essential.

The literary community, government, and literary organizations should work together to improve the literature of tribes. Literature has to be taken forward using various modern tools in the right way to be taken in the direction of prosperity.

Conclusion

Anti-tribal Literature Awareness and Reform in Society

The literature of tribes is a beautiful and rich field that is an integral part of Indian literature. This literature gains prominence through diversity, uniqueness, and connectedness to the land and reveals the cultural heritage of the tribes.

Main Features

1. Uniqueness and Diversity The literature of the tribes is famous for its uniqueness and diversity. It maintains its unique identity through language, art, music, dance, and tales.

2. Land-relatedness The literature of the tribes is deeply connected with their local land, environment, and lifestyle. It attempts to reveal their background, lifestyle, and emotional connection to the ground.

3. Establishment of values of life, the literature of the tribes is based on their values of life, religiosity, and social justice. In this, an effort is made to promote harmony and social equality.

4. Research and Exploration The literature of the tribes is the center of research and exploration for its unique role and richness. It involves securing one's historical, cultural, and social heritage.

5. Support of contemporary issues, tribal literature strongly supports current issues and challenges. It helps with the recent problems and challenges of its community and inspires societal improvements.

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References

1. Girase, S. (2016). The problems of Indian Tribal communities in current scenario. *International journal of development research*, vol.06(05), p. 7924-7927. <https://www.journalijdr.com/sites/default/files/issue-pdf/5356.pdf>
2. Vikas, M. (2016). Commentary on the Global Indigenous Peoples Movement: It's Stirring in India. *Journal of Law, Property, and society*, vol.02, p.1-16. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315075750_Commentary_on_The_Global_Indigenous_Peoples_Movement_It's_Stirring_in_India_Constitution_Within_a_Constitution_The_Treatment_of_Indigenous_Rights_in_Globalizing_India
3. Girase, S. (2016). The problems of Indian Tribal communities in current scenario. *International journal of development research*, vol.06(05), p. 7924-7927. <https://www.journalijdr.com/sites/default/files/issue-pdf/5356.pdf>
4. Vikas, M. (2016). Commentary on the Global Indigenous Peoples Movement: It's Stirring in India. *Journal of Law, Property, and society*, vol.02, p.1-16. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315075750_Commentary_on_The_Global_Indigenous_Peoples_Movement_It's_Stirring_in_India_Constitution_Within_a_Constitution_The_Treatment_of_Indigenous_Rights_in_Globalizing_India

Book

1. सहगल, पृ. (2019). रामाभील: जनजातीय संस्कृति एवं इतिहास का लोकनायक. आदिवासी लोक कला एवं बोली विकास अकादमी म.प्र. संस्कृति परिषद भोपाल का प्रकाशन वर्ष 2019, पृष्ठ क्र 30.
2. शर्मा, ब्रज (2012). आदिवासी विकास एवं सैद्धांतिक विवेचन (संस्करण षष्ठ) मध्य प्रदेश हिन्दी ग्रंथ अकादमी भोपाल.
3. तिवारी, शि (2010). मध्यप्रदेश की जनजातीय संस्कृति (संस्करण तृतीय) मध्य प्रदेश हिन्दी ग्रंथ अकादमी भोपाल.
4. शर्मा, श्री. (2009). जनजातीय समाज शास्त्र (संस्करण सत्रहवां) मध्य प्रदेश हिन्दी ग्रंथ अकादमी भोपाल.
5. Singh, A. k. (2008). Tribal development in India (1st ed.). Serials Publications, p. IX, X, XI, XII, XIII, XIV, XV, XVI, XVII.
6. श्रीवास्तव, ए. आर. एन. (2007). जनजातीय भारत (संस्करण द्वितीय) मध्य प्रदेश हिन्दी ग्रंथ अकादमी भोपाल. राम और रामराज्य आधुनिक परिप्रेक्ष्य, डॉ. कृष्णगोपाल मिश्र, जनजातीय लोक कला एवं बोली विकास अकादमी मध्य प्रदेश संस्कृति परिषद, मध्य प्रदेश जनजातीय संग्राहलय, भोपाल का प्रकाशन | <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ftJKlcmr18vAbcavHNXXAX5Z36WiocR1/view>
7. गोण्ड गीत - मध्यप्रदेश की गोण्ड जनजाति के पारम्परिक गीत - प्रो। शरीफ मोहम्मद- जनजातीय लोक कला एवं बोली विकास अकादमी मध्य प्रदेश संस्कृति परिषद, मध्य प्रदेश जनजातीय संग्राहलय, भोपाल का प्रकाशन | <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1qRvo8 IO6vzixTE9-OaeMe2V9G11OnvJJ/view>
8. स्वर्ग श्री कृष्ण द्वारा सीखी चौदह विद्याएँ और चौसठ कलाएँ, जनजातीय लोक कला एवं बोली विकास अकादमी मध्य प्रदेश संस्कृति परिषद, मध्य प्रदेश जनजातीय संग्राहलय, भोपाल का प्रकाशन | <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Drza11WTxH4kBXDJKnHz2pfUqExeu7EB/view>
9. प्रो. नर्मदा प्रसाद गुप्ता - चंदेल कालीन लोक महाकाव्य - आल्हा - प्रामाणिक पाठ, जनजातीय लोक कला एवं बोली विकास अकादमी मध्य प्रदेश संस्कृति परिषद, मध्य प्रदेश जनजातीय संग्राहलय, भोपाल का | <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t8O3N3x8vEDuu3dSKTB68QeeeASi0aU/view>
10. लोक साहित्यिक सन्दर्भ - बांग्ला एवं भोजपुरी साहित्य - हरिशचंद्र मिश्र, जनजातीय लोक कला एवं बोली विकास अकादमी मध्य प्रदेश संस्कृति परिषद, मध्य प्रदेश जनजातीय संग्राहलय, भोपाल का | https://drive.google.com/file/d/1FMjYGPM_e_A-a-OC6m2ux1rebl2cYcjz-/view
11. <https://mptribalmuseum.com/other-books.html>

Report

1. Government of India Ministry of tribal affairs. (2016-17). *Annual report 2016-17 socio-economic activities for tribal development*. Retrieved from <http://www.tribal.gov.in/writereaddata/AnnualReport/AnnualReport2016-17.pdf>
2. Government of India Ministry of Tribal affairs. (2015-16). *Annual report 2015-16 socio- economic activities for tribal development*. Retrieved from <http://www.tribal.gov.in/writereaddata/AnnualReport/AnnualReport2015-16.pdf>
3. Government of India Ministry of Tribal affairs. (2014-15). *Annual report 2014-15 Tribal welfare and development*. Retrieved from <http://www.tribal.gov.in/writereaddata/AnnualReport/AnnualReport2014-15.pdf>
4. Government of India Ministry of tribal affairs. (2014). *Report of the high level committee on socioeconomic, health and educational status of tribal communities of India*. Retrieved from <http://www.Indiaenvironmentportal.org.in/files/file/Tribal%20Committee%20Report,%20May-June%202014.pdf>
5. Government of India Tribal affairs statistics division. (2013). *Statistical profile of scheduled tribes in India 2013*. Retrieved from <http://www.tribal.gov.in/ST/StatisticalProfileofSTs2013.pdf>
6. Census of India 2011. (2013). *Schedule tribe in India, as revealed in census 2011, Dr. C. Chandramouli registrar general & census commissioner*. India Ministry of Home Affairs 03 May 2013. Retrieved from <http://www.tribal.gov.in/writereaddata/AnnualReport/ScheduledTribesinIndiaasRevealedinCensus2011.pdf>

7. सिन्हा, एस. (2014): सेंसस ऑफ इंडिया 2011, मध्यप्रदेश डिस्ट्रिक्ट सेंसस हेण्डबुक, श्योपुर, सीरीज 24 पार्ट गप्प ए, डायरेक्टोरेट ऑफ सेंसस आपरेशन्स, मध्यप्रदेश, भोपाल
8. सिन्हा, एस. (2014): सेंसस ऑफ इंडिया 2011, मध्यप्रदेश डिस्ट्रिक्ट सेंसस हेण्डबुक, श्योपुर, सीरीज 24 पार्ट गप्प ए, डायरेक्टोरेट ऑफ सेंसस आपरेशन्स, मध्यप्रदेश, भोपाल क्र 6 पृ 30

Magazine

1. चंदेल, प्र. (2018). भारतीय लोकमिथक. चौमासा, वर्ष 33, अंक 105, नवंबर 2017-फरवरी 2018, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 5.8.10.11.12.15-24.
2. शर्मा, शै. (2018). लोकसाहित्य एवं संस्कृति. चौमासा, वर्ष 33, अंक 105, नवंबर 2017-फरवरी 2018, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 25-30.
3. शर्मा, गु. (2018). लोक परंपराओं का भविष्य. चौमासा, वर्ष 33, अंक 105, नवंबर 2017-फरवरी 2018, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 31, 33.
4. शुक्ल, प. (2018). लोक कथा साहित्य. चौमासा, वर्ष 33, अंक 105, नवंबर 2017-फरवरी 2018, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 95-100.
5. मिश्रा, अं. (2018). पारंपरिक संस्कृति का बदलता स्वरूप. चौमासा, वर्ष 33, अंक 105, नवंबर 2017-फरवरी 2018, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 111, 112.
6. भानावत, क. (2018). आदिम गाजो बाजो का लोक. चौमासा, वर्ष 33, अंक 105, नवंबर 2017-फरवरी 2018, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 127-129.
7. दबे, श. सुं. (2018). नर्मदा प्रसाद गुप्तः लोक इतिहास और संस्कृति के अध्येता. चौमासा, वर्ष 29, अंक 90, नवंबर 2012-फरवरी 2013, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 14-19.
8. परिहार, श्री. (2018). नर्मदा तट का साहित्य साधकः बाबूलाल सेन. चौमासा, वर्ष 29, अंक 90, नवंबर 2012-फरवरी 2013, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 73.
9. पंवार, आर.एस. (2018). सहरिया गृह प्रकारः एक विश्लेषण. चौमासा, वर्ष 34, अंक 108, नवंबर 2018-फरवरी 2019, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 54.60.
10. जैन, पु. (2018). आदिवासी लेखन की वैचारिकी और उसका वर्तमान. चौमासा, वर्ष 34, अंक 107, जुलाई-अक्टूबर 2018, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 5-21.
11. धव, ड. (2018). लोकसाहित्य और संस्कृति. चौमासा, वर्ष 34, अंक 107, जुलाई-अक्टूबर 2018, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 32-34.
12. चक्रवर्ती, पु. (2018). वन और जनजातीय जीवन. चौमासा, वर्ष 34, अंक 107, जुलाई-अक्टूबर 2018, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 99-104.
13. चंदेल, प्र. (2017). भारतीय लोक अवधारणाओं की पृष्ठ भूमि. चौमासा, वर्ष 33, अंक 103, मार्च-जून 2017, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 11-18.
14. शुक्ला, अ. (2017). लोक संस्कृति और भारतीय समाज. चौमासा, वर्ष 33, अंक 103, मार्च-जून 2017, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 233, 234.
15. वर्मा, रा. (2017). लोकगीतों में धरिया. चौमासा, वर्ष 33, अंक 103, मार्च-जून 2017, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 207.
16. भानावत, म. (2015-2016). विवाह संस्कार एवं रीतियाँ. चौमासा, वर्ष 32, संयुक्तांक 98-99 जुलाई-अक्टूबर 2015, नवंबर 2015-फरवरी 2016, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 8.
17. जैन, नि. (2014). जनजातियों में मृत्यु संस्कार. चौमासा, वर्ष 31, अंक 95, जुलाई-अक्टूबर 2014, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 111-112.
18. गप्ता, नी. (2013-2014). जन्मसंस्कार. चौमासा, वर्ष 30, अंक 93, नवंबर 2013-फरवरी 2014, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 140-145.
19. सहगल, पू. (2013-2014). संस्कारों का महत्व. चौमासा, वर्ष 30, अंक 93, नवंबर 2013-फरवरी 2014, पृष्ठ क्रमांक 29-32.
20. निरगुणे, व. सहरिया. मध्यप्रदेश आदिवासी लोक कला परिषद् भोपाल का प्रकाशन, पृष्ठ क्र 1.